

Deep-tech driven inclusive and socially-aware circular material joining & welding for a safe future

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D6.2 External Evaluation Strategy and Report

(First Version)

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
CMW	Circular Material Welding
EES	External Evaluation Strategy
EU	European Union
KPIs	Key performance Indicators
KA2	Key Action 2
OBJ	Objective
EQAB	External Quality Assurance Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PMP	Project management plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
M	Month
N/A	Not Available
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

Table 1 Terminology

Terminology	
Evaluation	Systematic collection and analysis of information on the actual performance of a project. Its aim is to analyze the relevance, progress, success, and cost-effectiveness of the project. An evaluation compares planned results with the actual results of a project. It is a diagnostic tool
Monitoring	Continuing management exercise. When implementing a project, monitoring deals exclusively with the conversion of inputs into outputs. This exercise will help evaluate if what was supposed to be done really is. Adjustments to the project are possible when monitoring is done throughout the project management life cycle.

Performance indicators	Indicators that provide information (either quantitative or qualitative) on the extent to which the results of a project have been achieved. Evaluation is often confused with indicators used to evaluate. Any activity which aims at interpreting results, or data obtained from indicators, are part of an evaluation. To assure that the evaluation process leads to good decision-making, it must rest on correct and precise indicators.
DAC criteria	OECD DAC Network on Development Evaluation (EvalNet) has defined six evaluation criteria – relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability – and two principles for their use. These criteria provide a normative framework used to determine the merit or worth of an intervention (policy, strategy, program, project or activity). They serve as the basis upon which evaluative judgements are made
Relevance	Refers to the extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries, global, country, and partner/institution needs, policies, and priorities , and continue to do so if circumstances change.
Coherence	Refers to the extent to which the intervention is logically connected and mutually reinforcing with existing policies or other projects. It assesses how well the various components of an initiative work together towards achieving the intended goals and objectives
Efficiency	Refers to producing planned outputs within budgetary limits and established deadlines. For example: Was the implementation of the project professionally managed?
Effectiveness	Refers to achieving planned results and contributing to attain established goals and objectives. For example: To what extent were the project's objectives achieved?
Impact	A general statement of desired outcomes to be achieved over a specified period (the reasons for which the National Agency wishes to undertake the project).
Sustainability	Refers to the ability to maintain or support an intervention continuously over time .

Executive Summary

This document presents the first version of the deliverable, «**D6.2 External Evaluation Strategy and Report**», for the **WELDIFY** project. The External Evaluation Strategy (EES) serves as a structured and adaptable framework, designed to evolve with input from project partners over time. Specifically, its main objective is to define a rigorous evaluation methodology and establish key criteria for assessing the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of project deliverables, outcomes and results. Moreover, the strategy is aligned with both the specific objectives of the project and the overarching goals of the programme. In this framework, it will guide consortium partners in ensuring that the project maintains high standards throughout its implementation.

Developed for use by an external evaluator, the EES supports the preparation of two formal evaluation reports, an interim and a final report, covering the entire duration of the project up to month 36. This is the first version of the deliverable, which will be updated at Month 18 and Month 36 to reflect project progress and integrate new findings and data.

This report is structured into the following sections:

- **Introduction (Section 1):** The outline of the project's objectives and goals, which are derived from the broader aims of the Erasmus + program. Additionally, it highlights the purpose, relevance, and scope of the External Evaluation Strategy (EES).
- **Monitoring and Evaluation Approaches (Section 2):** The report reviews recognized monitoring and evaluation methods, based on the existing literature. The adapted methodologies will provide essential tools for assessing the progress, effectiveness, and overall success of programmes and projects.
- **Detailed Evaluation Strategy (Section 3):** This section provides an in-depth explanation of the selected monitoring and evaluation strategy, emphasizing its alignment with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the specific objectives of the Erasmus+ programme. Specifically, it includes the evaluation criteria, performance indicators and analytical tools that will be used throughout the evaluation process. Furthermore, an Impact Weight Assessment is conducted for each Work Package (WP), identifying the key results, their relative importance and the associated risks.
- The final section summarizes the main elements of the evaluation strategy. In addition, it will offer a guidance for future monitoring and evaluation processes, emphasizing the importance of continuous improvement in project effectiveness.

1. Introduction

The WELDIFY project, funded under the Erasmus+ Alliances for Education and Enterprises, aims to advance welding technologies and practices through strong collaboration among diverse organizations, including research institutions, vocational education and training (VET) providers, universities, SMEs, and consultancies. The project focuses on circular material welding (CMW), promoting cooperation, education, and training to support the development of a cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral CMW toolkit, which is designed to encompass all key aspects of the CMW training process, ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive learning experience.

Alliances for Education and Enterprises are transnational, structured and result-driven projects under KA2 of the Erasmus+ Program, in which partners share common goals and cooperate to foster innovation, new skills, a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial mind-sets. They bring together enterprises and both higher education and vocational training providers to work together in partnership. Operating within one economic sector or several different economic sectors, they create reliable and sustainable relations and demonstrate their innovative and transnational character in all aspects. In this context and in compliance with the objectives of the action, the WELDIFY's specific objectives are:

SO1: Develop an innovative cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral CMW toolkit (ECTS and ECVET compliant) uptaken by 5000 learners (VET/university/industry employees). The courses will be also uploaded on the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative Platform and will also be delivered to 500 learners with disabilities.

SO2: Develop a cutting-edge human-machine interaction toolkit for trainers in welding processes by integrating robotics to enhance safety and security (higher education, vocational education, corporate) that would be uptaken by 250+ VET/SME/higher education trainers.

SO3: Establish a robust quality assurance and certification framework for CMW, aligning with ISO standards.

SO4: Develop a Europass-enabled micro-credential certification framework for the envisioned CMW toolkit would enable at least 2000 learners (students, VET learners, workforce) to receive certification.

SO5: Establish a comprehensive cross-disciplinary platform for advanced learner analytics, market skills prediction and real-time learning content update (to reflect real time market needs).

SO6: Conduct work-based learning apprenticeships with 100 learners.

The EES for the WELDIFY project is outlined in this report, focusing on the explanation of the methodological approach and critical framework so as to access the quality, relevance, and

effectiveness of project deliverables, expected outcomes, and overall results. The main goal is the project's impact enhancement, efficiency, and long-term success. Within this framework, the evaluation criteria and analytical tools are detailed, along with a comprehensive overview of key results and outcomes from each work package, including their relative impact on the project's objectives.

The EES has been developed under Work Package 6 (WP6): «Monitoring and Evaluation», which ensures the effective and high-quality development of project content and activities. The specific objectives of WP6 include:

- Ensuring the compliance and proper formatting of project activities and outputs
- Verifying the traceability of project actions and outcomes
- Identifying and classifying potential issues or weaknesses in order to address them proactively
- Reviewing project results in relation to the intended impact
- Evaluating the outcomes according to each target group identified.

The methodology adopted in developing the WELDIFY EES is presented in Section 3.

2. Monitoring and Evaluation Approaches

Evaluation approaches and evaluation methods are both used to assess the effectiveness and impact of programs, policies, or interventions. However, they refer to different aspects of the evaluation process. Evaluation approaches refer to the overall framework or perspective that guides the evaluation. They define the philosophical, theoretical, and methodological principles that underpin the evaluation. Evaluation methods, on the other hand, are the specific techniques and tools used to collect and analyze data to evaluate the program or project. Methods can be quantitative (e.g., surveys, experiments, statistical analysis) or qualitative (e.g., interviews, focus groups, content analysis), and may vary depending on the evaluation approach used. An evaluation method is narrower than an evaluation approach, comprises a procedure outlining how to deal with empirical data, be it qualitative or quantitative: e.g., how to conduct different types of interviews, how to create and analyze datasets, how to conduct desk reviews of specific documents etc.

For monitoring and evaluation, there are several approaches that have been developed to address specific evaluation questions or challenges and they refer to an integrated package of methods and processes. Monitoring and evaluation approaches are essential for any organization for measuring the progress and success of any project or program. Every approach includes principles, methods and tools that can be used for projects that have the ambition to contribute to innovation, but they differ widely in their vision on reality, the on-going

processes, and their results and how to support, manage or adjust these processes. Deciding which method is the best depends heavily on the nature of the project, its context, and the monitoring and evaluation objectives

In general, the following approaches can be identified:

- Results-oriented approach,
- Participatory approach,
- Theory-based evaluation approach,
- Monitoring and Evaluation for learning approach,
- Case study evaluation approach,
- Impact Evaluation approach.

2.1. Results-oriented approach

This approach focuses on measuring the extent to which a project's original objectives and planned outcomes have been achieved, rather than simply tracking activities. It emphasizes assessing outcomes and impact, it relies on the use of SMART indicators: «specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound», in order to guide the monitoring and evaluation process and to track progress over time.

The results-oriented approach is based on assumptions of causality and linear change. In other words, it operates under the belief that: if certain actions are implemented, then specific outcomes will follow. This makes it a useful tool for strategic planning, as it encourages project teams to clearly define their goals and how they expect to achieve them. It supports the formulation and clarification of the project's intervention strategy (Van Mierlo, 2011).

While this approach is effective for projects with clearly defined objectives and pathways, it has limitations when applied to complex or system innovation processes. Innovation and collective learning often unfold in non-linear, unpredictable ways, making it difficult to identify direct cause-and-effect relationships. As a result, this approach may overlook the importance of shared learning and the development of a common understanding among stakeholders (Van Mierlo, 2011).

2.2. Participatory approach

The participatory monitoring and evaluation approach is a qualitative method that emphasizes the active involvement of key stakeholders, particularly the intended beneficiaries, in both the design and implementation of the evaluation process. Rather than being conducted solely by external experts, this approach engages those affected by the project to help access its progress and outcomes.

Participatory evaluations serves multiple purposes, two of the most common are:

1. Empowering beneficiaries to better understand, analyze and improve their own situations.
2. Generating more accurate and relevant findings by incorporating local knowledge and perspectives.

This approach can be used as a stand-alone evaluation method, or in combination with other approaches such as impact or theory-based evaluations. Consequently, it is especially suitable for projects where:

- The initiative impacts a diverse group of beneficiaries.
- Outcomes may emerge in varied and unpredictable ways.
- The focus is on social inclusion, empowerment, or community development.
- The organization conducting the evaluation follows a rights-based approach.

Participatory evaluations are valuable in contexts that prioritise inclusivity, ownership, and meaningful engagement throughout the evaluation process (Bakewell et al., 2003, Guijt 2014, ActionAid, 2016).

2.3. Theory-based evaluation approach

The theory-based evaluation approach is grounded in a clearly defined theory of change or logic model that explains how a project or set of interventions is expected to bring about change. As outlined in frameworks like the EIT Monitoring, Learning and Evaluation (MEL) model, a theory of change typically maps a sequence of results—from inputs and activities to outputs, outcomes, and ultimately, impact—highlighting the assumed cause-and-effect relationships at each step (EIT MEL, 2021). Theories of change may be very simple – such as the kind of logic model contained within a standard logical framework – or much more complicated. A theory-based approach normally attempts to assess change at each stage of the theory to test the linkages (assumptions) between different levels of change. Essentially, a theory-based approach sets out to test the theory to see if it holds true. If it does, the job of the evaluator is to produce a plausible case, with evidence, that shows what has changed, and explains how a development intervention contributed to that change (White, 2009). Theory-based approaches can only be used when there is some kind of predicted change to assess. They may not be

appropriate very early on in a project or programme before the project / programme has had time to contribute to changes at outcome or impact level. Equally, it would not be appropriate when a project or programme is genuinely exploratory – in other words when the potential outcomes / impact is not known and cannot reasonably be estimated beforehand (White, 2009).

A typical process for developing a theory of change includes several collaborative steps (Weiss, 1995):

- Define the long-term goal of the program—this should reflect a broader social or economic issue the project aims to address, often beyond the immediate project timeframe.
- Identify the key outcomes needed by the end of the project to move toward that goal (e.g., reducing disparities between different social or economic groups).
- Specify outputs and short-term outcomes that will support those key outcomes, such as the introduction of innovative learning materials or technologies.
- Design the necessary activities and interventions to achieve these outcomes, potentially tailoring them to the needs of different target groups based on factors like education or work experience.
- Assess available resources, including funding, staffing, institutional capacity, partnerships, and infrastructure needed to implement the interventions effectively.

Following a collective and iterative process the resulting project/programme theory must fulfill certain criteria: it must be plausible, doable and testable. It needs to be articulated in such a way that it can be open to evaluation; this is only possible where there is a high degree of specificity concerning the desired outcomes. Only then, the theory of change that is elicited should be interrogated to ensure that the underlying logic is one that is acceptable to stakeholders either because of the existing evidence base or because it seems likely to be true in a normative sense. The evaluator then takes the programme map generated through this process and, using various data (qualitative and quantitative) collection techniques as relevant, monitors and analyses the unfolding of the programme in practice and integrates the findings.

2.4. Monitoring and Evaluation for learning approach

The Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) for learning approach emphasizes continuous learning and improvement, rather than focusing solely on accountability or external reporting. It is a dynamic and iterative process that uses regular monitoring, feedback, and reflection to inform decision-making and support adaptive project management.

This approach encourages active stakeholder engagement throughout the evaluation process to identify what is working well, where challenges exist, and how the program can be refined. By doing so, it enhances the program's effectiveness and relevance over time.

The central goal of M&E for learning is to foster a culture of ongoing learning within organizations—where insights gained from implementation are systematically used to improve strategies, activities, and outcomes. Learning becomes an integral part of every stage of program planning and execution, helping teams to remain responsive and innovative in complex or changing environments.

2.5. Case study evaluation approach

Case-based approach focuses on the systematic generation and analysis of cases (sometimes known as case studies or stories of change). Cases may be based around any unit of analysis, such as people, communities, projects, programs, institutions, policies, or events. Most case-based approaches include both the analyses of individual cases, and analysis across multiple cases. They can be used in any type of work (e.g., service delivery, capacity development, policy influencing) and in any sector of work (e.g., health, education, governance). They are a valuable tool for assessing the program's effectiveness over time, as it enables researchers to compare the results of different interventions and track changes in program outcomes. However, they are not always the best approach if the need is to generate universal findings – that is findings that may be applicable in many different situations. For example, a set of cases designed to examine how community-based organizations influence local government practices in a specific locality may generate conclusions that could apply elsewhere within that locality, but the conclusions may not be relevant for other localities. This is because case studies tend to focus on change and contribution to change within a specific context. Outside of that context, any findings may not be valid (Stern et. al. 2012).

2.6. Impact Evaluation approach

Impact evaluation approaches aim to assess whether the predicted changes brought about through a project or programme have happened or not. The meaning of impact evaluation differs depending on how impact is defined. For example, some define impact narrowly, only including long-term changes in the lives of targeted beneficiaries. Others use wider definitions that also include changes in areas such as policies or capacities. However, there is generally broad agreement that an impact evaluation involves a few features that distinguishes it from other kinds of evaluation. Although other kinds of evaluation may cover one or more of the features in the list below, an impact evaluation would normally be expected to cover all of them:

- Impact evaluations seek to assess the changes brought about by a project or programme, rather than focusing on activities and outputs only;
- They aim to assess predicted change, although many cover unexpected or negative change as well;
- They attempt to assess the contribution of a development intervention (or set of interventions) to any identified change; and

- They usually follow a rigorous and accepted research methodology to identify change and contribution.

Impact evaluations can be carried out on any kind of work, including service delivery, capacity development, mobilization and policy influencing, and any sector of work from health through to governance. An impact evaluation can be applied at any level of work from small projects through to complex programmes covering multiple organizations, sectors, and geographic locations.

An impact evaluation can be carried out for the same reasons as any other kind of evaluation – e.g., to improve projects and programmes, demonstrate accountability, and contribute to wider learning. However, impact evaluations have the potential to provide more certainty about any findings, because they are more rigorous in their approach. On the other hand, they also tend to be more costly than other kinds of evaluation and may take longer to plan and implement. Therefore, the costs and benefits of carrying out an impact evaluation always need to be carefully weighed up (Stern 2015, Perrin 2012, Rogers 2012, ActionAid 2016).

A comparative analysis of the above approaches, in terms of their benefits and challenges, is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Monitoring and evaluation approaches

M & E Approach	BENEFITS	CHALLENGES
Results-Oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables accurate tracking of project progress, helping to identify challenges or achievements early on. • Monitors changes in different conditions and context over time. • Prioritises areas with the greatest need and strategic importance • Enhances the overall impact and effectiveness of the project 	<p>Data collection and analysis: Specifies how data are collected and stored, who is responsible for supplying the data, and who conducts the analysis.</p> <p>Information Presentation: Defines who can access the evaluation findings, how results are reported and shared, and in what format.</p> <p>Protocols: Establishes clear procedures to ensure data are presented in a meaningful, accessible way, using appropriate reporting standards.</p>

		<p>Limitations: Acknowledges constraints such as time, resources, or technical capacity that may affect the evaluation process.</p>
Participatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables a more comprehensive project evaluation by incorporating community members' feedback and lived experiences. • Enhances understanding of the local context and offers an effective means to assess project impact. • Highlights on the importance of both quantitative and qualitative data. • Ensures community voices are meaningfully, included throughout the evaluation process. • Promotes active collaboration among all stakeholders, contributing to more effective and sustainable development outcomes. 	<p>Stakeholder representation should be appropriate and inclusive, throughout the evaluation process.</p> <p>Methods of data collection and analysis should be reliable.</p> <p>Evaluation results should be used to inform future actions.</p> <p>Stakeholders must be able to interpret and apply evaluation results effectively to enhance their value and impact.</p>
THEORY-BASED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies potential gaps, solutions and areas for improvement and expansion. • Offers a thorough assessment of the project's overall effectiveness. • Enables critical examination of the underlying assumptions of the project and provides insights for refinement or 	<p>The theoretical assumptions guiding the research methods, sampling methods, and analysis techniques should be clear.</p> <p>Indicators and measurement tools must be clearly defined to ensure that each component of the theory is thoroughly examined and evaluated.</p>

	expansion to enhance outcomes	
Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) for Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Places strong emphasis on internal learning and continuous program enhancement. Fosters collaboration in data collection, analysis, and interpretation to uncover strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement. Engages a wide range of stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defining clear learning outcomes Developing appropriate indicators Stakeholder engagement Sustainability Attribution and causality Data collection and analysis
CASE STUDY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers detailed insight into the implementation and outcomes of a project. Serves as a practical assessment of how well the project is functioning, enabling timely adjustments. Identifies causes and any challenges that may affect the performance. Reveals experiential information from participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is essential to develop a research design that fits accordingly to the specific context and characteristics of the being studied. Confidentially issues Availability of resources and personnel, allocated to data collection and analysis.
IMPACT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aims to assess how a specific project or intervention has influenced a particular group. Examines both short-terms and long-terms effects, including any unexpected outcomes. Offers a more comprehensive understanding of how the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time limitations Complexity Difficulties to measure immediate outcomes, as some effects may take a long time to become clear. The presence of multiple factors and stakeholders

	<p>intervention affected its target audience.</p>	<p>makes it challenging to isolate cause-and-effect relationships and determine what specifically led to an outcome.</p>
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3. Evaluation Strategy

3.1. Evaluation Approach

The WELDIFY project is fully aligned with the requirements outlined to the program’s evaluation roadmap. Therefore, the EES is a key component for the proper implementation of the project, in accordance with the Better Regulation Guidelines¹ and the Erasmus+ legal base².

Specifically, the main objective of the EES is the methodical evaluation of the performance of the project. This designed process includes the comparison of the project’s outcomes with the initial expectations, which are identified in the impact assessment (D7.3), and the provisions of the relevant legislation. Therefore, the EES does not focus only on the expected results but also seeks to identify any unintended or unforeseen effects that were not previously anticipated or addressed in the impact assessment or the legislative framework. Additionally, the EES aims to draw definitive conclusions about the ongoing suitability of the intervention. It assesses whether the project continues to meet its intended purpose or if adjustments are necessary to enhance its effectiveness, relevance, and coherence. This assessment also considers the need to reduce any undue burdens or inconsistencies. In cases where the project no longer aligns with its intended goals, the EES may recommend its repeal.

In this framework, a result-oriented evaluation approach that focuses on monitoring and self-assessment of project progress towards specific outcomes and results will be followed. Specifically, the evaluation procedure will be carried out by an external evaluator, appointed by CERTH in collaboration with IMPACTSCI, with the agreement of the Strategic Committee (SC). The appointed evaluator possesses necessary skills and qualifications, including relevant experience in evaluation. He will also be working alongside the four members of the External Quality Advisory Board (EQAB). Together, they will perform quality checks at three levels for each output (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft). Moreover, The External Evaluator will

http://ec.europa.eu/smart-regulation/guidelines/toc_guide_en.htm

² Regulation No 1288/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing 'Erasmus+': the Union programme for education, training, youth and sport (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 50).

implement the external evaluation strategy described in this document, based on identified impact factors, results and outcomes which influence the overall impact. Furthermore, the Evaluator, will prepare two evaluations: a midterm and a final report, which will be integrated into the interim and final reports of the EACEA. The above process includes the monitoring of the implementation stages of the project and informing accordingly the SC, the EQAB and the other project's management bodies. On the other hand, the EQAB will continue to review the project's technical outcomes and provide non-binding advice to support further improvements. In the framework of Quality Control Panel (QAP), regular meetings will be held, with the participation of the External Evaluator with PC, Quality Assurance Manager (IMPACTSCI) and representatives of the consortium, presenting evidence from his thorough review. The timeline and set of evaluation material are defined during the project implementation by the WELDIFY Strategic Committee (SC).

This approach is goal-driven and requires a clear understanding of the desired results. It involves setting clear and measurable criteria and performance indicators, developing an action plan, and continuously tracking progress toward the project and program goals more accurately, related to the other approaches, allowing to identify any issues or successes early in the process. It is important to monitor systematically the progress and the effects of the implementation because in case of absence of such information, it will be difficult to evaluate the intervention appropriately and to rectify problems or improve delivery of the desired result.

In the selection of the approach, the overall program evaluation approach was also taken into account. Programme evaluation is following the same pattern, adopting a result-oriented approach aiming at assessing the effectiveness of the Erasmus+ actions in achieving the programme's objectives and the efficiency of the Programme and its European added value as well as the long-term results and impact of the predecessor programs. It also addresses the Programme's internal and external coherence, the continued relevance of its objectives, and the scope for simplification. Typically, results-oriented monitoring and evaluation follows a life-cycle approach – that is, an approach aligned with the key stages of the project and program cycle.

In this context, the Programme monitoring is done through a combination of tools:

- Analysis of Programme performance indicators;
- Analysis of the internal project reports (to check the progress, take remedial action, update action plans, and allow on-going data collection and preparation of progress reports);
- Monitoring missions (usually annual missions to review the performance of approved projects and the Programme for further improvements);
- Mid Term Evaluation of the Erasmus+ Programme;
- Final evaluation of the Erasmus+ Programme.

At the same time, and to be aligned with the Program's evaluation plan, the external evaluation methodology of the project/interventions is based on an explicit set of relevant tools that considers the following elements:

- Indicators, target values and sources of verification;
- Baselines for the indicators set by the project;
- Type of evaluations needed, their timing and results;
- Frequency and content of project progress reports (project coordinator and beneficiaries);
- Project timetable of implementation and reporting requirements.

A process line, depicting in simple steps the evaluation methodology that will be adopted, is reflected on **Figure 1** below

Evaluation findings are based on a wide range of data sources systematically triangulated i.e., cross-checked against each other: programme documentation, programme data and views of the managing bodies, views of direct beneficiaries as well as nonbeneficiaries, EU and national stakeholders, policy makers, programme countries, bodies in charge of implementation of other comparable programmes and the general public.

Data collection and review – Inputs for the interim and final evaluation reports

Progress/ Interim Reports

Interim/ progress reports present the interim, preliminary, or initial evaluation findings. They focus on events and tactical details like progress drivers and anticipated roadblocks. The goal of a progress report is to assess where the project has been and what are the next steps. The beneficiaries issue periodical progress/interim reports on a defined basis based on the provisions of the contract. The quality of the reports is supplemented by the relevant information, activities, and resource schedule of the reporting periods.

Outputs/ Activities/ Deliverables

Another important source of information are the internal documents, including reports, deliverables, and outputs. The final evaluation report reviews the actual progress of activities, in content and timing, and use of resources against what is planned and examine whether that also corresponds to what is reasonably needed. The consolidation of data produced during each reporting period, analysing the whole set of progress reports available at the expert's disposal to obtain the necessary knowledge and understanding of the state of play, ensure a sound analysis and draw of useful conclusions.

Interviews

Interviewing is used as a methodology for both quantitative and qualitative evaluation. The interviews are designed and organised on an “unstructured” set-up, notably informal and conversational discussion with representatives from the coordinating beneficiary in the basis of a qualitative approach, including only topic areas and themes rather than standard questions. During the interviews, data and narrative information are collected, in order to better understand the respondent's subjective perspectives. A standard indicative form interviews is proposed hereby:

- Short description of the participant profile.
- What is your general feedback from the project experience?
- Pros and cons according to your experience
- Has the project changed your way of thinking of work organization?
- Has the project changed your way of working actually?
- What are your general conclusions and recommendations?

The interviews with the involved stakeholders can be conducted through various ways: questionnaires sent via email or chatting apps, telephone calls, online interviews, face-to-face discussions etc.

Analysis and qualitative scoring Analysis

The analysis of the data and information collected is performed on the basis of data comparison between what has been delivered and what was contractually expected to be delivered on the foreseen timeframe and budget.

Scoring

Qualitative scoring based on a traffic light grading system is used (see **figure 2**). This provides a quick overview of the status of the interventions at the level of each monitoring question. A three-grade scale is adopted using the following categories: The grade is coherent with the finding; the justification of the grade emerges clearly from the analysis.

	<p>Green - good or very good</p>	<p>The situation is considered satisfactory, but there may be room for improvement. Recommendations are useful, but not vital to the intervention.</p>
	<p>Orange - with problems</p>	<p>There are issues to be addressed, otherwise the global performance of may be negatively affected. Necessary improvements do not however require a major revision of the logic and implementation arrangements.</p>
	<p>Red - off track or with serious deficiencies</p>	<p>There are deficiencies which are so serious that, if not addressed, they may lead to failure of the intervention. Major adjustments and revision of the intervention logic and/or implementation arrangements are necessary.</p>

Figure 1 – Traffic Light Grading System

The evaluation reports that will be elaborated throughout the project duration put specific focus on commenting on crosscutting issues (mainstreaming themes) and on the possible identification of lessons learned and good practices.

Conclusions and recommendations

The conclusions and recommendations of the interim and final evaluation reports will be drawn applying the key principles of the results-oriented monitoring methodology according to the following six DAC criteria of **relevance, coherence, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability**, that will be further analysed on Section 3.2.

3.2. Evaluation Criteria

The evaluation criteria's purpose is to support consistent, high-quality evaluation within a common framework. They provide a normative framework with which to assess a specific intervention. The criteria can also be used in processes beyond evaluation, including defining frameworks and indicators for monitoring and results management, funding approval, strategic planning, and intervention design, particularly to improve future interventions. Collectively, there is value in having commonly defined criteria that are similarly applied across interventions. The criteria also provide a consistent language across the development field, providing standardisation and allowing for comparison and learning across interventions. The evaluation criteria are not a methodology, and they are not the goals that an intervention is trying to achieve. Instead, they provide prompts for asking the right questions during the evaluation of an intervention.

Because every intervention (the entity being evaluated) is different, the evaluation process needs to be flexible, and the use of evaluation criteria should be thoughtful and adapted to the purpose and users. External evaluator should think critically about which criteria are most useful to support high-quality, useful evaluation that will be valuable to the intended users. The following six aspects and their related questions will assist in the thoughtful application of the criteria:

Context: What is the context of the intervention itself and how can the criteria be understood in the context of the individual evaluation, the intervention, and the stakeholders?

Purpose: What is the evaluation trying to achieve and what questions are most useful in pursuing and fulfilling this purpose?

Roles and power dynamics: Who are the stakeholders, what are their respective needs and interests? What are the power dynamics between them? Who needs to be involved in deciding which criteria to apply and how to understand them in the local context? This could include questions about ownership and who decides what is evaluated and prioritized.

Intervention (evaluand): What type of intervention is being evaluated (a project, policy, strategy, sector)? What is its scope and nature? How direct or indirect are its expected results? What complex systems thinking are at play?

Evaluability: Are there any constraints in terms of access, resources, and data (including disaggregated data) impacting the evaluation, and how does this affect the criteria?

Timing: At which stage of the intervention's lifecycle will the evaluation be conducted? Has the context in which the intervention is operating changed over time and if so, how? Should these changes be considered during the evaluation? The timing will influence the use of the criteria as well as the source of evidence.

The most important aspect of deciding how to use the criteria is relating them to the aim of the evaluation and its context and then building the evaluation criteria and questions around this purpose.

The criteria are not intended to be applied in a standard, fixed way for every intervention or used in a tick-box fashion. Indeed, the criteria should be carefully interpreted or understood in relation to the intervention being evaluated. This encourages flexibility and adaptation of the criteria to each individual evaluation. It should be clarified which specific concepts in the criteria will be drawn upon in the evaluation and why. The purpose of the evaluation should be carefully and clearly defined. Stakeholders involved in the evaluation should be included at this stage to ensure that they understand the goal of the evaluation and how it will be used.

Key questions to look at when determining the purpose of the evaluation include:

- What is the demand for an evaluation, who is the target audience and how will they use the findings?
- What is feasible given the characteristics and context of the intervention?
- What degree of certainty is needed when answering the key questions?
- When is the information needed?
- What is already known about the intervention and its results? Who has this knowledge and how are they using it?

Quality and ethical standards should inform subsequent thinking about methodological approaches, design, implementation, and management of the evaluation process.

When adjusting the criteria to a specific evaluation, it is also important to delve into causality and gauge the extent to which the evaluation will be able to attribute effects to the intervention being assessed. These considerations can help manage stakeholder expectations and determine which criteria will be covered in depth. This is most crucial for effectiveness and impact, but it is also indirectly applicable to, and may feed into, other criteria. For example, efficiency and sustainability could use the actual (or projected) benefits attributed to the intervention as assessed under effectiveness and impact.

The key points that are considered, where relevant, as regards the selection of the DAS evaluation criteria and their adaptation to the external evaluation purpose of WELDIFY project, are provided below. It should be noted that coherence is jointly evaluated together with the relevance.

Relevance and coherence

- Design process of the project proposal/methods to involve local stakeholders (local ownership).
- Successful synergies and networking with stakeholders inside and outside the project.
- Coordination, complementarity, and EU added value.
- Complementarities and synergies established with other interventions.
- Intervention logic, Monitoring, and learning

- Log frame and indicators.
- Knowledge/Learning system put in place.
- Reporting and monitoring systems put in place.

Efficiency

- Internal management and communication, including internal knowledge management practices.
- Funding modalities (when conducive to ensuring relevance, efficiency, effectiveness and/or sustainability of the project).
- Implementation modalities found particularly innovative, efficient and/or cost-effective.

Effectiveness

- Effectiveness of activities such as: dialogue models/ methods used to increase civil society participation/ to increase dialogue between state authorities and CCIIs/ also between CCIIs and other businesses of the private sector.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: Capacity development, i.e., training and mentoring methods, processes, follow-up.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: Advocacy, i.e., strategies used to promote legislative changes, etc.
- Effectiveness of activities such as: External communicational policies and practices.

Sustainability

- Actions to support the sustainability of local stakeholder activities.
- EU practices, i.e., coordination between other networks.
- Existence of exit/ handover strategies.

Another criterion that is horizontally applied/considered throughout the evaluation of all criteria is the **impact** which corresponds to the broader change in the political, social, economic and/or environmental global context which tends to be long-term and stems from the combined effort of the project activities. It is a detectable improvement in the lives of people based on economic, social, cultural, institutional, environmental, technological changes.

In brief, the **DAC criteria** used for drafting the conclusion and recommendations of the evaluation reports are broken down as follows:

Relevance #1. Are we doing the right things?

Relevance looks at the relationship between the needs and problems in society and the objectives of the intervention. Things change over time, certain objectives may be met or superseded; needs and problems change, new ones arise.

The extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries' global, country, and partner – institution needs, policies and priorities, and continue to do so if circumstances change.

- Do the interventions constitute an adequate response to the current needs and rights of the target groups / end beneficiaries?
- Are the interventions adapted to the present institutional, human, and financial capacities of the partner government and/ or other key stakeholder(s) with a role in implementation?
- Do the interventions show a high degree of alignment with key EU priorities?
- Is the choice of IP/method of implementation proving to be appropriate?
- Do all key stakeholders demonstrate effective commitment to the objectives of the interventions (i.e., ownership)?

Coherence #2. How well does the intervention fit?

Coherence is connected with relevance. While relevance assesses the intervention at the level of the needs and priorities of the stakeholders and beneficiaries that are directly involved, coherence goes up to the next level and looks at the fit of the intervention within the broader system. Both relevance and coherence consider how the intervention aligns with the context, but they do so from different perspectives.

Effectiveness #3. Is it working?

The extent to which the intervention achieved, its intended objectives, and its results, including any differential results across groups.

- Are the outputs being achieved with the expected quality?
- To what extent are results inclusive i.e. ensuring the fair distribution of effects across different groups of the population?
- Does the intervention effectively influence the partner's relevant policy and interventions?
- Is the intervention having any unintended positive or negative effects? Were the negative effects considered for possible (risk) mitigation?

Efficiency #4. Are we doing things well?

Efficiency considers the cost-effective and timely relationship between the resources used by an intervention and the changes it generates (which may be positive or negatives). Resources include staff, purchases, time and money spent on fixed costs, running costs and administrative burden. The extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver results, in an economic and timely way.

- Are the implementation mechanisms proving to be appropriate to achieve planned outputs and contribute to outcomes?
- Are the inputs/ resources provided by the various stakeholders (still) adequate for achieving the planned results?
- Has the intervention encountered any delays and was the planning revised accordingly?
- Is spending in line with the budget?

Sustainability #5. – Will the benefits last?

Sustainability relates to the continuation of benefits from an intervention after major support has been completed. The probability of continued long-term benefits. The resilience to risk of the net benefit flows over time. It has various dimensions: social, economic, political, environmental, financial, institutional, etc.

- Are key stakeholders attaining the necessary capacities (incl. institutional, human, and financial) to ensure the continued flow of benefits/ services?
- Is access to the benefits generated by the intervention affordable for target groups over the long term?
- Has the private sector been sufficiently involved with a view to contributing to the sustainability of the interventions?
- Does the intervention increase resilience to shocks and pressure (by addressing specific dimensions of fragility and their root causes)?

Impact #6. – What difference does the intervention make?

Impact addresses the ultimate significance and potentially transformative effects of the intervention. It seeks to identify social, environmental, and economic effects of the intervention that are longer term or broader in scope than those already captured under the effectiveness criterion. Beyond the immediate results, this criterion seeks to capture the indirect, secondary, and potential consequences of the intervention. It does so by examining the holistic and enduring changes in systems or norms, and potential effects on people's well-being, human rights, gender equality, and the environment.

- Has the intervention caused a significant change in the lives of the intended beneficiaries?
- How did the intervention cause higher-level effects (such as changes in norms or systems)?
- Did all the intended target groups, including the most disadvantaged and vulnerable, benefit equally from the intervention?

- Is the intervention transformative – does it create enduring changes in norms – including gender norms – and systems, whether intended or not?
- Is the intervention leading to other changes, including “scalable” or “replicable” results?
- How will the intervention contribute to changing society for the better?

Evaluating relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, sustainability, and impact is often challenging. Impact is the one that can often be the most challenging to evaluate and understand. In **Table 2** the main challenges involved, together with some suggestions on how the external evaluator should proceed, are summarised.

Table 2: Challenges of Evaluation criteria (Source OECD)

CRITERIA	CHALLENGES	HOW TO ADRESS: EVALUATOR
Relevance	There are many national and international stakeholders to consider who have multiple and potentially competing priorities and needs	A strong analysis of relevance should consider potential and actual trade-offs in responses to needs. The relevance of beneficiaries should be the most important consideration when looking at needs and priorities. Ownership and participation are also helpful for managing this challenge and in ensuring that competing priorities are accounted for and, where possible, balanced.
	Understanding if an intervention has clear and appropriate objectives and how they were determined.	To make a strong assessment of relevance, an intervention’s objectives are a critical starting point. This can be a challenge if they are not clearly articulated. Evaluators should critically review the extent to which objectives are sufficiently challenging, reflect the needs of both the intended beneficiaries and the capacities of stakeholders, and explore how these objectives were identified and verified. The suitability of objectives might be further explored under impact to understand whether the objectives contributed to important, transformational changes. In this instance, evaluators should engage closely with programme stakeholders to

		<p>understand the programme’s objectives, how they were defined and ascertain whether a contingency plan is/was in place. They should assess whether and to what extent these are based on a sound analysis of needs and context. This will form an important starting point for understanding relevance.</p>
	<p>The intervention lacks a clearly articulated theory of change, logic model and/or other explicit design rationale.</p>	<p>Assessment of relevance is aided by a theory of change, logic model and/or other explicit design rationale as this provides important insights for assessing relevance of design. Evaluators should identify if this exists and, where necessary, work with stakeholders to help them reconstruct or clearly articulate the theory of change as a starting point for the evaluation.</p>
	<p>The context changed over time, but it is unclear if – and how – the intervention was adapted</p>	<p>Unfortunately, adaptations are not always well documented. It is necessary to first describe what changes occurred, and how the intervention was (or was not) adapted, in order to then evaluate relevance. If it is clear that the context has changed significantly in ways that might have affected relevance, the evaluators should consult intervention documents (such as annual or quarterly reports, monitoring data, and, if possible, communications such as meeting minutes, announcements to staff and participants) to “reconstruct” the changes that were made and identify key decision points and what drove those decisions.</p>
	<p>Different contexts/countries - large volume of policy documents, data, and informants to be assessed.</p>	<p>Challenges can only be solved by applying qualitative assessments based on the available sources of data/information. It is also important to assess evaluability during the inception of an evaluation and be open and</p>

Coherence		transparent about limitations. It should be flagged when data sources cannot be accessed. Understand the legislative environment and organizational policies and use knowledge to design appropriate primary data collection and analysis plans.
	Assessing coherence across all relevant policy areas can lead to a very broad scope.	Collaborate with the evaluation manager to ensure priorities and scope are clearly defined at the start of the evaluation.
	The mandates of some evaluation departments may focus only on humanitarian and development assistance, limiting their scope to assess coherence questions across government.	Special attention should be paid at the evaluation design stage to define and refine the scope of the evaluation, and to operationalise how coherence would be explored in line with evaluation departments' mandates – or to outline limitations in doing so.
	Organisations restricting access to data due to data protection legislation and/or organisational policies.	Ongoing discussions should be held with the evaluation team to support access to data and to develop suitable risk mitigation strategies.
	Lack of appropriate, informative, or disaggregated data.	The availability of data (e.g. a lack of baseline or mid-term assessments) can inhibit the measurement of the achievement of objectives as causality is then more difficult to attribute and it is harder to determine who is contributing what. Baseline data can be reconstructed but this is generally less precise and reliable than properly assembled baseline data. Other approaches evaluators can take include: 1) triangulation and validation of data that is available; 2) use of alternative methods; and 3) the construction of a contribution story.

Effectiveness	Working with poorly phrased, vague, or difficult-to-measure objectives/purpose statements.	Ensure that intervention objectives are verifiable, realistic, and aligned with current international standards for development interventions in the inception phase of an evaluation. The indicators for measuring the achievement of the objectives should also be validated according to generally accepted criteria such as SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Timely). Ideally, this process should be undertaken in a participatory manner between the evaluators and evaluation managers.
	Attribution of results	The issue of attributing causality or determining contribution is a challenge in evaluating effectiveness, particularly over the longer term. The construction of a contribution story and devising appropriate triangulation of data streams can support the evaluator to identify whether results can be attributed to the intervention being evaluated.
Efficiency	Finding suitable comparisons	Evaluators usually struggle to find perfect matches, so they use what is available. Yet, they must be cautious in making comparisons and should undertake a sensitivity analysis. For example, efficiency in fragile and conflict-affected situations should only be compared with similarly challenging environments.
	Navigating different concepts of efficiency and the associated methods and tools	The literature on the economic concepts of efficiency is extensive and can be consulted by evaluators to decide on which methods and tools are most appropriate given the evaluation at hand.
	Lack of adequate expertise on efficiency analysis	Ensure there is an understanding on what is needed to conduct an efficiency analysis and how to incorporate it into the evaluation process (both in terms of approach and expertise).

	<p>Data and measurement</p>	<p>Available data on benefits, results and costs can be hard to obtain. For example, impact evaluations may provide quantified estimates of changes in outcomes due to the intervention while, generally speaking, leaving out estimates of costs, let alone full costs.</p>
	<p>Time considerations</p>	<p>Both in economic appraisal and in evaluation of efficiency, choices between time periods when resources are used and when results are delivered are a crucial aspect. Results and full costs (e.g. environmental costs) may accrue over many years, so the actual efficiency during the course of the programme, or at the time of the evaluation, may not reflect the entire picture.</p>
<p>Sustainability</p>	<p>If the intervention has not achieved its intended results (assessed via effectiveness), positive unintended benefits or made contributions to impact.</p>	<p>In the case that the intervention has had no benefits, the analysis of sustainability becomes redundant. Evaluators should be clear and open about the limitations of evaluating sustainability and consider focusing on other criteria.</p>
	<p>Timing of the evaluation</p>	<p>Evaluations will often take place during the lifespan of the intervention or may occur at a point where sustainability is not yet evident. Therefore, evaluators should consider focusing on the conditions for sustainability if the intervention is still being implemented or has very recently ended. They should provide a robust assessment of prospective sustainability by identifying factors in the operating environment that could favor sustainability.</p> <p>In this sense, gender analysis is a key and will provide useful and relevant information on the consistency of the structural changes achieved and their effect on reducing inequalities.</p>

	<p>Evaluating factors likely to influence sustainability.</p>	<p>Contextual factors that support (or undermine) prospective sustainability can be assessed qualitatively and quantitatively. These include but are not limited to stakeholder ownership and engagement, absorptive capacity, political will, and national resource availability.</p>
<p>IMPACT</p>	<p>Clarity on what impact means as a concept for the relevant stakeholders and users of the evaluation.</p>	<p>Agree at the outset which definition is being used, whether the OECD DAC terminology or a different concept, and follow this consistently. Check with stakeholders regularly during discussions if their interpretation of the term has changed.</p>
	<p>Clarity on what impact was intended for this intervention and how it would be achieved.</p>	<p>This depends on the original design of the intervention and availability of a clear results framework, with a theory of change. If this does not exist, a theory-based evaluation of impact (which is highly desirable) would be difficult, so it will need to be reconstructed which includes reference to specific target groups. Some interventions typically have goals that are too broad and inflated beyond the scope of what the intervention can achieve.</p>
	<p>Identifying the degree to which the intervention causes the impact.</p>	<p>Mapping the pathways of contribution or attribution as appropriate from the intervention to results when these may be less traceable/explicit at higher levels. Use of methods such as contribution analysis can be helpful here.</p> <p>Drawing on specific guidance/methodologies on how to measure impact, explore options and make deliberate and realistic choices on methods driven by the purpose of the evaluation, context, questions to be answered, data availability and resources available for the evaluation and their feasibility. A key question is whether the methods will simply assess the size of the</p>

		impact for that intervention, or also identify why and how it occurred.
	Availability of data including baselines and indicators.	For assessing higher-level effects, data can be particularly challenging, including lack of baselines and indicators. This is partly an evaluability question to be considered at the outset of the evaluation but also informs the choice of suitable methods to draw on different types of qualitative and quantitative data in the best possible way.
	The intervention has significant unexpected or unintended effects.	It is often difficult to capture unintended or unexpected results as they are often left out of monitoring frameworks and data collection. To capture what is most important for beneficiaries and other people affected by the intervention (positively or negatively) evaluators should remain open to looking beyond the formal project documents and expected data. The relative significance of the effects will likely vary across stakeholders.

Table 2 Challenges of Evaluation criteria (Source OECD)

3.3. Key Performance Indicators

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, external evaluation methodology will be based on the earlier expectations, which have developed in the context of the impact assessment (D7.3). Impact assessment set the basis to start measuring and monitoring defined indicators that will be reiterated and extended based on the project's evolution and proposed WELDIFY solution.

Those key performance indicators (KPIs) are a valuable management tool to monitor progress (and allow adjustments if needed) during the implementation of the project activities and to evaluate the degree of success in achieving its objectives.

KPIs should be "S-M-A-R-T" which stands for:

- **Specific:** Indicators should be crystal clear, focusing on who is doing what and how. The data collected should directly relate to the objective without any confusion.
- **Measurable:** If an indicator cannot be measured progress cannot be tracked down. Hence, once the indicator is clear and specific, it becomes measurable in various ways.
- **Achievable:** The indicator should reflect realistic changes that can be linked to the intervention.
- **Relevant:** The indicators should be a valid measure of the outcome and should be backed by research and expertise.
- **Timely:** The indicators need to be timely in terms of data collection, reflecting the resources available. They should also match the timing of the outcome changes and impact.

SMART indicators can help track progress effectively and ensure that everyone understands what's being measured and why (Gouédard, 2021). It must be kept in mind that a logical system, where different indicators contribute to producing an overall understanding of the different dimensions might influence the achievement of desired outcomes.

The definition of the KPIs assists to properly assess how the impact might vary over time in respect to the following given dimensions:

- **Societal:** Considers the impact that WELDIFY has on its learners, as well as other users considered as potential targets of interest.
- **Governance:** Considers whether institutions are able to use WELDIFY to partially overcome potential differences in social capital, through their good governance as well as cross-sectoral cooperation and partnerships.
- **Environmental:** Considers whether WELDIFY does directly or indirectly contribute to enhance a healthy relationship with the earth and its resources and establish more sustainable behaviors in its users.
- **Economic:** Considers whether industries adopting WELDIFY change their employability, income, operating costs, productivity, and competitiveness over time.

A prioritized set of indicators and their measurements defined and selected by the beneficiaries, were presented in the first version of the Impact Assessment Plan of the project (D7.3). The defined indicators are based on three variables:

- **Importance for the project:** The extent to which the indicator aligns with the project's goals and objectives,
- **Feasibility:** The practicality and ease of data collection and measurement for each indicator,
- **Effort Needed:** The resources, time, and effort required to measure the indicator effectively.

The final **KPIs**, derived from the above variables and dimensions, are presented in Table 3 below:

Dimensions	Themes	Indicator	Measurement Unit	Measurement Method
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	CMW modules developed and integrated into University curricula	No. of Modules	Complete learning pack
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	CMW modules developed and integrated into VET curricula	No. of Modules	Complete learning pack
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	No. of train-the-trainers' modules	No. of Modules	Complete learning pack
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	No. of trained learners on CMW	No. of registrations	Record/log keeping
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	No. of trained trainers in CMW	Number of certifications	Record/log keeping
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	No. of learners involved in blended work-based learning secondments	No of registrations	Record/log keeping
SOCIAL	Learning Experience	Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path	Pre and post assessment	Pre and post assessment (before and after the training)

Societal	Accessibility	No. of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project	No of certifications	Record/log keeping
Societal	Accessibility	Make online education more inclusive	Pre and post assessment	Pre and post assessment (before and after the training)
Societal	Acceptability	No. of companies engaged in the WELDIFY platform	No of registrations	Record/log keeping
Societal	Acceptability	No. of universities and VET centres that will uptake the WELDIFY platform	No. of institutions	Record/log keeping
Societal	Acceptability	No. of modernised university and VET related CMW curricula	No. of Institutions	Record/log keeping
Societal	Experience Satisfaction	Learner satisfaction with regards to the WELDIFY online platform	1-5 scale index	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction
Societal	Local & Regional Engagement	No. of social media	No. of people reactions	Record/log keeping

		engagement/impressions		
Societal	Local & Regional Engagement	No. of website visitors	No of websites views	Record/log keeping
Societal	Local & Regional Engagement	No. of people accessed from partners' countries	Number of open days participants	Record/log keeping
Societal	Local & Regional Engagement	No. of contacts	Number of contacts reached via online dissemination materials	Record/log keeping
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Learner digital competence increase	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Learner green competence increase	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Learner entrepreneurship competence increase	1-5 point scale for EntreComp	Self-assessed EntreComp survey (pre and post training)
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery	1-5 point scale for DigCompEdu	Self-assessed DigComp survey

Economic	Upskilling and employability	No of dropouts from university/VET	No of learners	Comparing drop-outs in year 1 and in year 3 learners database
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Make CMW workforce more productive (quant)	Productivity Metrics	Checking company reports
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)
Economic	Upskilling and employability	Increase of employability	Percentage	Comparing yearly statistics
Governance	Regional funds and investments in PM	Amount of funding obtained to sustain WELDIFY activities	Euro	Combined budget from new projects
Governance	Policy making	No. of policy makers interested in using WELDIFY platform	No. of Policy Makers	Record/log keeping

For each of the above KPIs, a **target value**, that need to be met until the end of the project's implementation, was set. The project has set very ambitious targets aiming at contributing to the Programmes' overall achievements.

Table 3 List of Indicators and target values

Indicator	Target Value
CMW modules developed and integrated into university curricula	5
CMW modules developed and integrated into VET curricula	5
Number of train-the-trainers' modules	5
Number of trained learners on CMW	5000
Number of trained trainers in CMW	30%
Number of learners involved in blended work-based learning secondments.	250
Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path.	100
Number of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project.	500
Make online education more inclusive.	45%
Number of companies engaged in the WELDIFY platform.	100
Number of universities and VET centres that will uptake the WELDIFY platform.	50
Number of modernised university and VET related CMW curricula	25
Learner satisfaction with regards to the WELDIFY online platform.	>85%
Number of social media engagement/impressions	100.000
Number of website visitors	5000

Number of people accessed from partners' countries	900
Number of contacts	1.021.000
Learner digital competence increase	35%
Learner green competence increase.	30%
Learner entrepreneurship competence increase.	35%
Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery.	25%
Number of dropouts from university/VET	25%
Make CMW workforce more productive (quant)	20%
Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant).	35%
Increase of employability	15-30% increase in 6-12 months
Amount of funding obtained to sustain WELDIFY activities.	500.000
Number of policy makers interested in using WELDIFY platform	20

3.4. Work Package Analysis

In this Section, the results and outcomes expected to be achieved in the context of the project as well as a preliminary assessment of the significance and influence of the anticipated outcomes, priority level and potential risks that may prevent the smooth implementation, along with the timeline and budget for each WP, will be presented.

More specifically, in the external evaluation reports, an analysis of the data and information collected will be performed on the basis of data comparison between what has been delivered and what was contractually expected to be delivered according to the foreseen timeframe and budget. The analysis will be done per WP and deliverable that are contractually expected to have been completed/ delivered during the reference period, for the interim evaluation report and until the end of the project, for the final evaluation report.

3.4.1. WPI: Project management and coordination

WPI ensures the proper implementation and coordination of the project. The specific objectives are to manage the WELDIFY Consortium, ensure communication, monitor project advancement, and oversee project risks and mitigation measures, maintain the link with the EACEA, oversee legal, contractual, IPR, ethical and gender matters and ensure a mentoring/coaching mechanism among the beneficiaries towards better facilitating overall project management. In this context two deliverables will be implemented:

D1.1 Project management plan (PMP): a report containing all internal management and coordination procedures.

D1.2 Data management plan (DMP): a document explaining the WELDIFY data management strategy.

Both outputs/ deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the

deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	Start Month: 1 End Month: 36
	Budget: 209.987,50 €
	Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, financial and administrative risks.
	Priority: Both deliverables are of high priority and need to be implemented at M1. D1.1 is an important deliverable and the first milestone of the project that need to be developed and approved in the kick-off by all partners and EQAB during the first month of the project.

3.4.2. WP2: Circular Material for Welding (CMW) training content development

WP2 is linked to OBJ1 (Develop an innovative cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral CMW toolkit) and OBJ2 (Develop a cutting-edge toolkit for trainers) of WELDIFY, aiming to: develop an advanced digital circular material toolkit for over 5000 learners, with a strong emphasis on quality and circular materials. Additionally, it aims to develop a circular material welding train-the-trainers toolkit, equipping trainers with the skills and resources needed to revolutionise welding processes. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

D2.1 CMW toolkit for trainers and learners: a compendium of documents covering content for

10 modules (trainers and learners): 600 slides with voice/video overlay, 10 storyboards, 2 booklet (300 pages), collection of 20 demonstrative videos, 2 interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool (360 multiplechoice questions) and 2 WebQuest per module related to work-based learning practices. Languages & translations: EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE.

D2.2 ECTS & ECVET Certification Documents: A collection of ECTS & ECVET accreditation processes. The objective is to achieve dual accreditation ECVET for vocational education and training and ECTS for higher education by following the EQAVET and EQUIS quality standards for course embedment in formal education.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (number of produced training modules and related material), the existence of weaknesses while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	<p>Start Month: 1 End Month: 12</p>
	<p>Budget: 435.490,00 €</p>
	<p>Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, Competitive courses.</p>
	<p>Priority: Both deliverables are of high priority and need to be implemented at M12. D2.1 is the cornerstone of the project, as it pertains to the comprehensive development learning material. D2.2 is a key process to ensure compliance with EQAVET and EQUIS quality standards.</p>

3.4.3. WP3: Micro Credential certification framework

WP3 relates to OBJ3 of WELDIFY (Develop a micro-credential certification framework for CMW-related micro courses) and has as sub-objectives to develop a micro credential certification framework for WELDIFY (for both the CMW training toolkit and train-the-trainers toolkit), introduce an operational framework for the institutionalization of the micro credential system and develop and standardize the assessment for the micro credentials. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

D3.1 Micro Credential Framework Document: an integrated report covering the results of the T3.1 and T3.2, regarding micro-credential certification criteria and Micro-credential assessment development.

D3.2 Assessment and Certification Tools: an automated Europass digital credential system embedded with the WELDIFY platform.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	<p>Start Month: 13</p> <p>End Month: 18</p>
	<p>Budget: 182.435,00 €</p>
	<p>Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay.</p>
	<p>Priority: D3.1 and D3.2 are medium priority and need to be implemented during M13 and M16. WELDIFY digital credential launched is an important deliverable and the fourth milestone of the project.</p>

3.4.4. WP4: WELDIFY CMW Platform

WP4 relates to OBJ4 of WELDIFY (Develop a cross-disciplinary platform) and has as sub-objectives to confirm and refined the platform requirement analysis (functional and technical) performed in the preparation phase, develop, test, and integrate the platform modules/services, populate the platform with content and prepare it for the pilots. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

D4.1 WELDIFY Platform: The WELDIFY platform successfully launched and tested.

The deliverable will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for the deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If the deliverable has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	Start Month: 18 End Month: 24
	Budget: 264.825,00€
	Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, Platform deployment
	The D4.1 is considered to be medium priority and will be implemented at the second year of the project M22. The successful finalisation of the platform as well as the integration of the work from WP2 and WP3, is an important deliverable and the fifth milestone of the project.

3.4.5. WP5: Work-based learning pilots

WP5 relates to OBJ5 of WELDIFY (Pilot the training courses and the platform) and has as sub-objectives to define the pedagogical methodology for blended work-based learning (in

company and via the WELDIFY platform), recruit companies and trainees/apprentices for the PM pilots, implement 6 pilots of 3 months each and identify learning opportunities/improvements for the learners and trainers and institutionalize the work-based learning framework in the education providers' and industries' operations. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

D5.1 WBL (work-based learning) PILOTS: It regards the successful implementation of a 3 month-pilot in Greece (2), Romania, Serbia, Spain, Sweden with learners engaged and certified.

D5.2 Evaluation & Improvement Report: an integrated report with the progress and the evaluation, including recommendations for improving WP2, WP4 based on WBL and Mass Pilot correction.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (at least 100 in-person pilot participants) the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	<p>Start Month: 18</p> <p>End Month: 36</p>
	<p>Budget: 395.900,00€</p>
	<p>Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, not reaching the participants targets, Date sharing reluctance</p>
	<p>The deliverables are of low priority and will be implemented during the second phase of the project. The successful implementation of the physical pilots is the sixth milestone of the project that need to be implemented up to M26.</p>

3.4.6. WP6: Monitoring and Evaluation

WP6 ensures the effective and qualitative project content and activity development and has as sub-objectives to safeguard the compliance and format of the project’s activities and outputs, to certify traceability of the project’s actions and outcomes, to recognize and categorize potential problems or weaknesses in the project’s actions and results with the purpose of remedy them, to review the project’s results vis-à-vis expected impact and to assess the project’s results per identified target-group. In this context the following deliverables will be implemented:

D6.1 Quality Assurance and Report: An integrated report containing the quality assurance plan and key performance indicators, including the results of the two periodic quality reviews.

D6.2 External Evaluation Strategy and Report: An initial report explaining the external evaluation approach (present report), will be completed by one interim and one final updated report will be issued as part of the external evaluation activities.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	Start Month: 18 End Month: 36
	Budget: 121.712 €
	Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay,
	D.6.1 and D.6.2 (present document) are of high priority and need to be implemented up to M3 and M6 accordingly. Process and content quality standards implementation is an important deliverable and the eightieth milestone of the project that need to be implemented up to M36.

3.4.7. WP7: Dissemination, Exploitation & Impact

WP7 aims to ensure that WELDIFY reaches its impact and sustainability. Its sub-objectives are to maximise project visibility and its impact by demonstrating the scale of impact stemming from the project activities, to diffuse and multiply capacity and project excellence within and beyond the project consortium (EU-wide scale of impact), to identify synergies with other related projects and exchange knowledge in order to reuse, bind and exponentially facilitate the impact and result sustainability, to better facilitate the quadruple helix participatory engagement process and foresight exercises, to actively influence policy and contribute to regional development, facilitate the achievement of the institutional, regional, national and international impact, formalize, institutionalize each component of WELDIFY platform, and to devise a 10-year sustainability strategy for the WELDIFY platform and secure the required resources (tangible, non-tangible). In this context the following deliverables will be implemented

D7.1 Communication and dissemination plan: a report ensuring a well-coordinated dissemination and communication.

D7.2 Communication and dissemination material, tools and events: a report presenting all communication and dissemination material developed and events organized and participated. These will include: (a) project website (content will be made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE), logos, document templates & social media accounts; (b) partner-level (decentralized) mailing list with selected target groups (GDPR compliant) of at least 25 000 contacts; (c) 6 newsletters (digital) with limited printed version (600) distributed to at least 25 000 contacts in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT; (d) 6 videos developed and disseminated to 25 000 contacts (videos will be in English with subtitles in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT); (e) 3 policy briefings (15 pages each) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT; (f) 8 open day dissemination events that will be hosted by (each) partner; (g) At least 6 appearances in TV/radio/conventional media will be produced.

D7.3 Impact measurement matrix with a preliminary impact assessment: a report introducing an impact measurement tool (methodology) that will build upon the quality, monitoring, dissemination, and progress activities even from the project implementation timeline in order to pave the way for impactful outcomes.

D7.4 WELDIFY sustainability, exploitation commercialization plan: A 6-step plan that would generate revenue while also improve the platform's offering.

The deliverables will be evaluated as regards their quality, their degree of completion, their contribution to the achievement of the set targets (25.000 contacts, 6 newsletters, 6 videos, 3

policy briefings, 8 open day events, 6 appearances in media), the existence of weaknesses, while potential suggestions for further improvement will be presented. The means of verification for each deliverable will be listed at the end of the evaluation, proving that the deliverable has been partially or fully completed. If any of the deliverables has not been produced or seems to be unavailable while drafting the evaluation reports, the source of verification will be characterized as N/A (not available).

	Start Month: 1
	End Month: 36
	Budget: 264.290€
	Risks: Quality, Lack of communication, Implementation delay, platform deployment, limited impact of dissemination
	D7.1, D7.3 are of high priority and need to be implemented up to M3. The last one is considered to be low priority, and it should be implemented until the end of the project.

4. Conclusions

The evaluation methodology is specially designed to ensure the delivery of high-quality outcomes aligned with the objectives of both Erasmus+ and the WELDIFY project. This framework is fundamental for developing external evaluation reports (both interim and final) for the WELDIFY project.

Section 1: Introduction and Project Objectives

The first section introduces the project, outlining its objectives and goals in alignment with Erasmus+ guidelines and overarching objectives.

Section 2: Evaluation Approaches

It explores various evaluation approaches from academic and professional literature, each offering a comprehensive set of methods and processes for assessing project and program progress and success. A comparative analysis highlights the strengths and limitations of each approach, informing the selection of the most appropriate methodology for the WELDIFY project. This choice was guided not only by the approaches' merits and drawbacks but also by the specific nature, context, and monitoring and evaluation objectives of the project.

Section 3: Detailed Evaluation Methodology

3.1 Evaluation Approach: A results-oriented approach was chosen, prioritizing monitoring and self-assessment of project progression towards defined outcomes and results. This method stands out for its ability to accurately track project success, facilitating early identification of issues or achievements and focusing on high-priority areas.

3.2 Evaluation Criteria and Tools: The section further identifies and analyses the evaluation criteria, indicators, and analytical tools. The process includes data collection and review, stakeholder interviews, qualitative scoring (using a traffic light system), and conclusions and recommendations drafted in line with the six DAC criteria (relevance, coherence, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability), adapted specifically for the WELDIFY project.

3.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): This subsection emphasizes KPIs defined in other project deliverables as essential for monitoring activity progress and evaluating success in achieving project objectives. These KPIs are designed to be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and timely, with clear target values.

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